

West End,
Wootton,
Woodstock,
Oxon,
1/8/73

Dear Beatrice,

Many thanks for your two letters.

Points arising:

Colour film can be freely sent out of Oman. It would be a first class idea if you could arrange to stay with the Philips. To put myself in your place it would break my heart to have to spend my excavation money on exorbitant hotel bills. I trust we can arrange something for the others too.

I assume you will be bringing with you a few copies of your Antiquity article. It would be a very good move if you could hand over in person a copy to the two or three most deserving people.

yours,

A handwritten signature in dark ink, appearing to be 'A. J. ...', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

P.S. Thanks for giving me a Doctorate in your last letter, but I do not have one yet!